

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PARATHYROID HORMONE AND HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE AMONG LOCAL POPULATION OF PAKISTAN

Dr Saira Ibrahim¹, Dr Ayesha Shaheen², Dr Afzal Hussain³

¹Wazirabad Institute of Cardiology, Gujranwala, ²Jinnah Hospital Lahore, ³District Head Quarter Hospital Hafizabad.

Article Received: March 2019

Accepted: April 2019

Published: May 2019

Abstract:

Introduction: Depression affects 350 million people around the world with a lifetime risk of 7%. Depression is likely to cause a 5.7% increase in the global burden of disease by 2020 and is to become the leading cause of disability worldwide by the year 2030.

Objective of the study: The main objective of the study is to analyze the relationship between parathyroid hormone and high blood pressure among local population of Pakistan.

Methodology of the study: This cross sectional study was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore during April 2018 till September 2018, with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. The data was collected from 200 hypertensive patients who visited the OPD of the hospital regularly. All those patients who have the history of smoking were excluded from this study. 5 mL of fasting blood sample was taken and analyzed for serum calcium, phosphorous, albumin, PTH, and hemoglobin. Serum calcium, phosphorous, and albumin were measured. BP was obtained using an automatic BP monitor. Three measures were taken at rest in a sitting position, with intervals of 5 min between the measurements. The average from the last two measurements was taken for analysis.

Results: The data were collected from 200 hypertensive patients. The mean age of the entire population was 45.7 ± 11.2 years. An overwhelming amount of the population was either unemployed (n = 296, 72%), married (n = 388, 94%), had a monthly income of less than PK Rs. 20,000, and were in the "low" category of the socioeconomic status (n = 321, 78%). Amongst the educational status, most of the population had received primary or no education (n = 277, 67%).

Conclusion: It is concluded that underlying causes of depression need to be addressed and community programs need to be initiated to raise awareness regarding long-term complications of untreated depression, especially in hypertensive patients.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Saira Ibrahim,**

Wazirabad Institute of Cardiology, Gujranwala.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Saira Ibrahim et al., A Comprehensive Study on Relationship between Parathyroid Hormone and High Blood Pressure among Local Population of Pakistan., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(05).

INTRODUCTION:

Depression affects 350 million people around the world with a lifetime risk of 7%. Depression is likely to cause a 5.7% increase in the global burden of disease by 2020 and is to become the leading cause of disability worldwide by the year 2030. Similarly, hypertension is one of the leading causes of global mortality and disability [1]. In 2010, it had been estimated that a 31.1% of the global population was hypertensive. Accountable for 9.4 million deaths annually, hypertension is responsible for a variety of diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases, renal failure, and stroke [2].

Numerous studies in humans and experimental models have shown that alterations in calcium homeostasis are associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular complication. In particular, changes in systemic calcium metabolism are thought to play an important role in the regulation of blood pressure [3]. Thyroid gland along with the parathyroid glands and heart share a close relationship arising in embryology. In ontogeny, the thyroid and heart migrate together [4]. There is a strong physiological relationship between the two organs, which is affirmed by predictable changes in cardiovascular functions across the entire range of thyroid disease states. Many symptoms and signs recognized in patients with overt hyperthyroidism and hypothyroidism are due to increased or reduced action of thyroid hormone on the heart and the vascular system, respectively [5].

Increases in parathyroid hormone (PTH) have been associated with changes in the vascular tone and renin angiotensin system. Hyper functioning parathyroid glandular disorders have been for long associated with an increased risk of hypertension, though a causal relationship is still not established [6].

Objective of the study

The main objective of the study is to analyze the relationship between parathyroid hormone and high blood pressure among local population of Pakistan.

Methodology of the study

This cross sectional study was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore during April 2018 till September 2018, with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. The data was collected from 200 hypertensive patients who visited the OPD of the hospital regularly. All those patients who have the history of smoking were excluded from this study. 5 mL of fasting blood sample was taken and analyzed for serum calcium, phosphorous, albumin, PTH, and hemoglobin. Serum calcium, phosphorous, and albumin were measured. BP was obtained using an automatic BP monitor. Three measures were taken at rest in a sitting position, with intervals of 5 min between the measurements. The average from the last two measurements was taken for analysis.

Statistical Analyses

The data were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 21.0. Comparisons between the two groups were done using the t test or the chi-square, where appropriate.

RESULTS:

The data were collected from 200 hypertensive patients. The mean age of the entire population was 45.7 ± 11.2 years. An overwhelming amount of the population was either unemployed ($n = 296, 72\%$), married ($n = 388, 94\%$), had a monthly income of less than PK Rs. 20,000, and were in the "low" category of the socioeconomic status ($n = 321, 78\%$). Amongst the educational status, most of the population had received primary or no education ($n = 277, 67\%$). High BP was present in 34% of the whole sample, and another 16% were taking medication for hypertension.

Variable	Total Score (p-value)	Depression Class (p-value)
Sex	0.009	0.026
Age	–	0.005
Marital Status	0.355	0.438
Educational Status	0.000	0.000
Employment Status	0.003	0.047
Monthly Income	–	0.003
Socioeconomic Status	0.008	0.027
Average Systolic Blood Pressure	0.148	0.175
Average Diastolic Blood Pressure	0.006	0.009
Severity of Hypertension	0.604	0.847
Dietary	0.119	0.233
Physical Activity	0.025	0.016
Smoking	0.017	0.031

Years Since Smoking	–	0.168
Alcohol Consumption	0.049	0.095
Prescription for Medicine	0.902	0.858
Compliance with Medicine	0.344	0.164
Number of Medicine Taken	0.566	0.455
Family History of Hypertension	0.022	0.028
Family History of Depression	0.002	0.002

Table 01: Analysis of relationship hypertension and parathyroid hormone

DISCUSSION:

A number of studies have investigated the effects of subclinical hyperthyroidism on the heart, showing that this condition may be associated with various abnormalities of cardiac structure and function. The cardiovascular disorders associated with subclinical hyperthyroidism may be a direct effect of thyroid hormone disturbance or may reflect an increased arterial pressure level in these patients [7]. There are no consistent studies proving that arterial BP rises in such patients. Recent meta-analyses of five large studies evaluating the incidence of hypertension in these patients did not reveal increased BP levels in individuals with suppressed serum TSH levels and free thyroid hormones within the reference range [8].

The more consistent abnormalities found in patients with subclinical hyperthyroidism are increased heart rate, prevalence of supraventricular arrhythmias, endothelial dysfunction and increased LV mass. This enhancement of LV mass is often associated with rise in systolic function and impaired myocardial relaxation. The rise in LV mass is due to concentric remodeling and is related to the duration of subclinical hyperthyroidism rather than to levels of circulating thyroid hormones [6]. A greater percentage of hypertensives with depression (40.1%) were found in our study, as opposed to depression patients with hypertension (21.2%) by Grimsrud, et al. in South Africa suggestive of depression being more likely to develop as a comorbid of hypertension than vice versa [8]. The deductible reasons for this high prevalence of depression amongst hypertensive patients include the possible mental impact of being aware of having such a lifelong condition and vicious cycle of economic constraints in low socioeconomic settings, health care costs, the resultant stresses, and further disability [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that underlying causes of depression need to be addressed and community programs need to be initiated to raise awareness regarding long-term complications of untreated depression, especially in hypertensive patients.

REFERENCES:

1. Everts ME, Verhoeven FA, Bezstarosti K, Moerings EP, Hennemann G, Visser TJ, et al. Uptake of thyroid hormone in neonatal rat cardiac myocytes. *Endocrinology*. 1996;137:4235–42.
2. Davis PI, Davis FB, Lin HY, Mousa AS, Zhou M, Luidens MK. Translational implications of nongenomic actions of thyroid hormone initiated at its integrin receptor. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab*. 2009;297:E1238–46.
3. Fommei E, Lervasi G. The role of thyroid hormone in blood pressure homeostasis: Evidence from short-term hypothyroidism in humans. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2002;87:1996–2000.
4. Streeten DH, Anderson GH, Jr, Howland T, Chiang R, Smulyan H. Effects of thyroid function on blood pressure: Recognition of hypothyroid hypertension. *Hypertension*. 1988;11:78–83.
5. Nilsson IL, Aberg J, Rastad J, Lind L. Maintained normalization of cardiovascular dysfunction 5 years after parathyroidectomy in primary hyperparathyroidism. *Surgery*. 2005;137:632–638.
6. Bergus GR, Mold JW, Barton ED, Randall GS. The lack of association between hypertension and hypothyroidism in a primary care setting. *J Hum Hypertens*. 1999;13:231–5.
7. Allon M, Harrow A, Pasque CB, Rodriguez M. Renal sodium and water handling in hypothyroid patients: The role of renal insufficiency. *J Am Soc Nephrol*. 1990;1:205–10.
8. Skowsky WR, Kikuchi TA. The role of vasopressin in the impaired water excretion of myxoedema. *Am J Med*. 1978;64:613–21.
9. Franklin SS, Jacobs MJ, Wong ND, L'Italien GJ, Lapuerta P. Predominance of isolated systolic hypertension among middle-aged and elderly US hypertensives: Analysis based on National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) III. *Hypertension*. 2001;37:869–74.
10. Gifford RW, Prisant LM. The importance of hypertension in the geriatric population. In: Prisant LM, editor. *Hypertension in the Elderly*. 1st ed. Totowa, NJ: Humana Press; 2005. pp. 3–9.